

SustAIIn / Liv Work

CENTRE OF
EXCELLENCE OF
ARTIFICIAL
INTELLIGENCE
FOR SUSTAINABLE
LIVING AND
WORKING

ADVANCING AI FOR SUSTAINABLE WORLD

Launched in 2023, the SustAIInLivWork Centre of Excellence (CoE) for Sustainable Living and Working was established to pioneer cutting-edge solutions powered by Artificial Intelligence (AI). The CoE focuses on driving innovation across four critical domains: industry, energy, transport, and health, addressing pressing challenges with sustainable, AI-driven advancements.

It is built on
strategic
collaboration
between
key national
partners:

Lithuania's four leading universities –

and advanced international ones –

These partners contribute their expertise to enhance value creation through advanced AI technologies.

MAIN ACTIVITIES OF THE CENTRE

AI LABORATORIES AND SYSTEMS

Intelligent systems modelling, business analytics, and sandbox environments with test-before-invest AI labs for external organisations.

PRACTICAL TRAINING AND EDUCATION

Value-added training programmes and courses that integrate best practices for implementing AI solutions while prioritising sustainability in the private and public sectors.

SYSTEMS DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION

AI solutions implementation, dual-environment testing, and certification for compliance and reliability.

DATA ANALYSIS

Customised data storage and computing infrastructure with 3A data services: analysis, annotation, and anonymisation for AI applications.

NEW GENERATION INTELLIGENT SOLUTIONS

Personalised Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) solutions providing higher levels of understanding while maintaining human oversight of AI systems.

PATENTS

New patents focused on delivering ethical, sustainable, robust, and high-quality intelligent technology performance.

BENEFITS FOR BUSINESS

HIGH-VALUE, PERSONALISED TRAINING

INFLUENCE RESEARCH DIRECTION

ACCESS TO FACILITIES AND EQUIPMENT

RISK-FREE AI TRIALS

POOL OF INNOVATIVE IDEAS

EXPANDED R&D CAPACITY

GET IN TOUCH

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PARTNER WITH US

to drive AI innovations that transform sustainability across Lithuania and beyond!